

Mobile energy recovery and storage: Multiple energy-powered EVs and refuelling stations

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ABSTRACT

It is widely accepted that electrical vehicles (EVs) for goods and people have a crucial role to play in energy transition towards carbon neutrality. Despite significant progress in recent decades, challenges remain in charging times of EV batteries and range anxiety of drivers, compared with vehicles powered by liquid fuels which are several times more energy dense than Li-ion batteries. This perspective article examines two solutions that have the potential to address the challenges: the conversion of diverse forms of wasted energy into electricity (e.g. vibration) and the reduction of battery power for the provision of ancillary services (e.g. cabin thermal comfort).

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1. Introduction

Replacing fossil fuel powered vehicles with electrical vehicles (EVs), enabling zero-emission transportation, has become one of most important pathways towards carbon neutrality. The driving power for EVs is supplied from an on-board energy reservoir, i.e. a lithium-ion battery pack. Charging woes and range anxiety due to limited battery capacity are the Achilles' heel of EVs. Under mild weather conditions, ~80% of the energy stored in EV batteries can be used to power the wheels [1]. This is significantly reduced when EVs are used in cold winters due to two major reasons: low winter ambient temperature limits the maximal capacity of lithium batteries, and EV heating system for warming up both the battery pack and the cabin consumes the battery power. The same applies to hot summers when cooling demand is high. To achieve a longer travelling range, the wasted energy needs to be minimised and/or recovered, and the capacity of on-board energy storage must be improved. Accordingly, technical solutions to resolve the challenges can be split to two categories: (a) harvest diverse forms of energy en route, convert them to electricity and store such energy in battery as top-up, for powering wheels and other on-board

electronic equipment; (b) directly store diverse forms of energy from extravehicular sources while parked, e.g., charge and store both thermal energy and electricity, respectively, for HVAC and power battery packs. In this paper, we review recent energy recovery and storage technologies which have a potential for use in EVs, including the on-board waste energy harvesting and energy storage technologies, and multi-vector energy charging stations, as well as their associated supporting facilities (Fig. 1). The advantages and challenges of these technologies are summarised.

2. Recovery of diverse forms of energy for storage: en route

2.1. Mature technologies: electromagnetic and photovoltaic effects

Kinetic energy recovery systems (KERSs), also called regenerative braking, are able to recover part of kinetic energy dissipated during braking and store the recovered energy for use when needed [2]. Commercially, a KERS contains two technological paths: mechanical KERS based on flywheels [3,4] and electrical KERS based on a motor generator [5,6]. Electrical KERSs are more suitable for EVs because their electrical motor and electrical generator share the same internal structures through an electromagnetic principle. The roles of the motor and generator can be interchangeable by determining if the required torque is positive or negative. When the torque serves to slow down the vehicle, the wheels are electrical generators, converting the kinetic energy of the vehicle to electricity and storing the energy in the battery pack.

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Fig. 1. A graphical illustration of energy harvesting/storing technologies for electrical vehicle integration.

Tesla was the first to integrate this electrical KERS in their EV model in 2007 [7]. Literature reported that up to 50% of the total braking energy can be recovered by the electrical KERS system, thus increasing the travelling range by 8–25% [8]. A main drawback limiting the use of electrical KERS in EVs is that continuous charging and discharging while driving may reduce the life span of batteries.

Photovoltaic semiconductor materials can be integrated with EVs for harvesting and converting solar energy into electricity. Solar energy has the advantages of being free to charge, widely available and has no global warming potential (zero-GWP) which has the potential to reduce GHG emissions by 400 Mtons per year [9]. It has been reported theoretically that a hybrid EV, equipped with a solar panel system with a 360 V Li-ion polymer battery, could pump out 100 kWh energy [10]. This has also been demonstrated in an EV

prototype with a 200 W photovoltaic module and a 19.2 kWh Li-ion battery, which showed that, with the photovoltaic module, the total travelling range was extended by 13.4 km over two sunny days [11]. Solar powered EVs are hardly seen on the road, and rarely commercialized by the automobile industry although the technology can be viewed as a developed technology. The primary reason for this is that solar radiation is unstable and highly dependent on weather, global latitude, and orientation of solar panels. As a result, a photovoltaic system at charging stations is a more preferred option for collecting solar energy for back-feeding to the grid than that installed on an EV for harvesting solar energy en route.

2.2. Piezoelectric effect

Piezoelectric effect, generating electrical charge under

mechanical stress, normally provides three times the energy density than the electromagnetic effect. It has therefore attracted the attention of many scientists and researchers in the automobile industry to investigate the feasibility of using a piezoelectric generator in automobiles to harvest energy from, for instance, wasted mechanical stress in the suspension system and/or tyres. Lead zirconate titanate (PZT), a piezoelectric ceramic, is an excellent option for use in metallic leaf spring plates due to its flexibility, temperature range and stability under humidity [12]. As cyclic stress loading/unloading is constantly applied to the tyres while the vehicle moves, making it a good application scenario for piezoelectric generators. For example, piezoelectric composites, made of Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) based polymers sheets, can be attached to the inner surface of a tyre. Mechanical energy in the form of longitudinal stretching and releasing of the piezoelectric composite sheet due to cyclic deformation of a rotating tyre can be harvested and converted to electricity [13]. The power output has been shown to reach 42.08 W at a vehicle speed 108 km/h [14]. Such an electrical output is sufficient for powering the on-board electronics such as charging a mobile phone [15]. Clearly, the application of piezoelectric generators in automobiles is not restricted to EVs, but can also be used in any vehicle especially for heavy duty vehicles, because larger stress variance is favourable for recovering more energy. In EVs, using piezoelectric technology for energy recovery can improve the travelling range by refuelling the power battery pack, and achieving a better energy efficiency [16].

2.3. Thermoelectric effect

Seebeck effect enables semiconducting thermoelectric generators (TEGs) capable of reversibly converting thermal energy to electricity in the presence of a temperature difference [17]. Such TEGs have been investigated for a variety of applications, including power plants [18], and combustion engines (~700 K) and/or exhaust systems (~500 K) for converting waste heat into additional electrical power [19,20]. BMW, Lincoln [21], and Renault [22] have been developing the TEG technology for their vehicles since 2010. For example, the maximum power output of 712 W was achieved by BMW [23] on a test bench, with fuel efficiency improvement of >1.2%. Although TEGs have been developed for over ten years for internal combustion engine powered vehicles, two major drawbacks remain that affect large-scale deployment of TEGs on EVs for energy recovery. First, TEGs have a low efficiency, converting about 1–7% of thermal power into electrical power, which is determined by the structure of the semiconductor stacks and the stability of the temperature difference under working conditions [24]. Second, there is a lack of high-temperature heat source (e.g., above 350 K) on-board EVs to maintain the temperature difference and ensure a viable thermal energy recovery [25]. Thus, waste heat from the battery pack, brakes, and even tyres can be potential heat sources in EVs. Due to the fast thermal response of TEGs, battery thermal management systems for EVs are able to heat the battery in winter via e.g. a heat pump, and for cooling the battery and generating electricity in summer via the thermoelectric generator [26]. For example, Coulibaly et al. showed that the use of TEGs to harvest energy from the brake discs of vehicles can generate at least 4 W of output power [27]. Michelin claimed that, with the development of flexible TEGs [28,29], they can recover thermal energy from tyres [30] - a temperature difference of about 30 °C could be created at a vehicle speed of 100 km/h. In general, vehicle electrification may alter the thermoelectric prospects from energy recovery and storage to a compact thermal management system for both battery and cabin. EVs require new thermal management solutions for the battery while it works at a high power output and/or during ultrafast charging, which are not required in conventional vehicles.

2.4. Elastocaloric effect

Heating the battery and cabin in winter and cooling the cabin in summer of an EV consumes a large portion of the energy stored in the battery, which can lead to significant shortening of the travelling range of EVs. This could be alleviated by using technologies based on ferroic coupling effects produced during changes to the magnetic field (magnetocaloric - MC), electrical field (electrocaloric - EC), or stress field (mechanocaloric - MC) [31]. The MC includes the elastocaloric effect (eCE) and barocaloric effect (BCE) which can be based on for example shape memory alloys (SMAs) [32]. They are efficient methods for converting mechanical energy into thermal cooling energy with the advantages of miniaturised device volume, quiet working conditions, and fast thermal responses [33–35]. Most importantly, they do not rely on an electrical input. They have therefore been regarded as a promising technology to replace the small scale vapor-compression systems for on-board air conditioners, especially in EVs. Xiao et al. [36] reviewed the stress-induced cooling mechanism of shape memory alloys (SMAs) covering Ni–Ti-, Cu-, Fe-, and Heusler-based shape memory alloys for applications in elastocaloric refrigeration [37] and energy recovery [38]. Elastocaloric cooling technology is still at an early stage. The first fully integrated elastocaloric refrigerator prototype in the world was developed by Chen et al., in 2022 [39] based on Nickel-titanium based SMAs. Their elastocaloric refrigerator was able to generate 3.1 W cooling power, reducing the temperature of a 0.9 L compartment by 9.2 K. The wasted vibrational energy while driving could provide sufficient mechanical energy input for the purpose, through cyclic stretching of the solid refrigerant (polycrystalline Ni–Ti shape memory wires). The advantages, such as compactness, high cooling efficiency, and no global warming potential, make such type of technologies suitable for on-board cooling in EVs.

2.5. Triboelectric effect

Triboelectric nanogenerators, TENGs, have attracted much attention in recent years, for their compactness, low-cost, sensitive to mechanical input, and high energy conversion performance [40]. Materials for TENGs vary from solid (i.e., polymer [41] or fabric [42]) to liquid [43], as well as liquid-solid interfaces [44]. Various prototypes of TENGs based on different structures have been reported, including a rolling spherical structure [45], duck-shaped structure [46], and membranes [47]. TENGs have been utilised to harvest various forms of energy as a sustainable electrical power supply. Mao et al. [48] and Bhamre et al. [49] scavenged friction energy from rolling tyres through a single-electrode TENG for improving travelling range of EVs. Their energy conversion efficiency was reported as 10.4%.

A project funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme [50,51] proposed a low-cost and environmentally friendly technology for the recovery of abundant waste energy into electricity for EVs. One of the aims of the project is to build a novel shock absorber for EVs to convert ambient heat and vibrational energy into electricity based on nanotriboelectrification. The principle is based on the intrusion/extrusion of a liquid, e.g. water into/out of a non-wetting porous medium as illustrated in Fig. 2, where two processes occur at the same time: the liquid cools based on the liquid cooling phenomena; and the liquid and the liquid-solid interface acquire opposite electrical charges according to the liquid-solid contact triboelectrification [42]. The application of the two processes in the proposed shock-absorber enables passive harvesting of both thermal energy and mechanical energy while driving, and generation of electricity to refuel the EV power battery. The state-of-the-art technologies

Fig. 2. Energy balance for (a) conventional oil-pressed, (b) electromagnetic, and (c) nanotriboelectrification shock absorbers.

based on the triboelectric effect, such as triboelectric generators, use mechanical energy as the input, converting mechanical energy to electricity [52]. The nominal conversion efficiency (e.g., mechanical energy input over electricity output) is normally about 10% [48,49]. In the new approach as illustrated in Fig. 2, both the vibrations and thermal energy from the environment are used as the inputs, and the nominal conversion efficiency could be as high as 82% [53,54]. Moreover, a nominal conversion efficiency of electrical power greater than 100% could be achieved ($COP > 1$). It can therefore be regarded as a pumped electrical generator.

Although very little current research focuses on the applications of TENGs in EVs, prototypes with various structures, novel concepts and designs can be found in the literature [52]. The TENG-based energy harvest and conversion technologies could have a significant impact on future automobile sector, especially for the range extension of EVs.

3. Direct refuelling energy for storage: from a station

In EVs, there are multiple thermal management requirements for diverse purposes, including cabin thermal management (e.g. cabin heating and cooling for thermal comfort etc.), battery thermal management (BTM), and refrigeration in refrigerated trucks etc. Efficient and effective thermal management methods can play a key role in maintaining adequate travelling range, safeguarding components from deterioration, ensuring passenger comfort, and preventing food quality and medicine functionalities. In recent years, Thermal Energy Storage (TES) technology, as a passive thermal management solution, has attracted more and more attention for applications in EVs due to enhanced cycle life, high overall efficiency, simple control procedure, fast heating and cooling response time and low energy costs [55]. For these applications, charging stations with hot and cold reservoirs are needed, integrated with existing charging station infrastructure to charge the battery and TES concurrently.

TES can be based on one or more of the three forms: (a) sensible heat stored in a liquid or a solid medium, (b) thermochemical energy stored and released via a reversible chemical and/or physical process, and (c) heat of fusion (latent heat) through the use of Phase Change Materials (PCMs), as illustrated in Fig. 3 [56,57]. Sensible heat storage is the most commonly used TES technology [58], where the heat introduced to the storage medium increases its temperature. Latent heat storage is more attractive than sensible heat storage due to high energy density and constant temperature

during phase change process [56–58]. TES based on thermochemical energy storage (TCES) offers inherently much higher energy density than sensible and latent heat based TES [59]. Currently, TCES development remains at the early stage to technology due to both various technical and economic challenges [60]. Therefore, latent heat storage using especially solid–liquid PCMs has been the mostly studied method for EV thermal managements due to balanced energy density, technical maturity and economics [56].

3.1. Cabin heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC)

HVAC includes heating, ventilation, and air conditioning, which is an essential subsystem of a vehicle. HVAC has two levels of functionality in EVs: the first is to ensure operational safety by defogging and de-icing the windshield and windows, and the second is to maintain cabin comfort by controlling temperature, relative humidity, and air velocity [61]. So far, Vapor compression refrigeration - Dedicated heater (VCR-DH) is the most commonly used HVAC system in EVs (electrical heating) and hybrid EVs (fuel heating) owing to its convenient substitution, low cost and serviceability [55]. Based on these, HVAC based on electrical heating is one of the primary consumers of power in a EV, consuming the most energy among all auxiliary systems [62]. It has been reported that HVAC systems can reduce the travelling range of EVs by 30–40%, depending on the size of the HVAC and the driving cycle [63,64]. An efficient HVAC system to minimize this energy consumption is a key to improve the performance of EVs. TES provides an alternative and promising solution to HVAC in EVs. The research on TES based HVAC systems in EVs can be divided into three categories: TES for cooling, TES for heating, and TES for both cooling and heating.

There have been some studies on installing an extra TES in a vehicle (usually underneath the rooftop or in headliner) simply to decrease heat load and maintain thermal comfort for passengers. This can save energy by avoiding dramatic temperature rise and significant humidity drop in vehicle cabins when parked under sunlight [65–68]. Most of these studies used a simple design and installed a TES unit for reducing cabin peak temperature under the sun with the cabin temperature being still higher than the comfortable temperature. Therefore, a conventional air conditioning system still needs to work to reduce the cabin temperature further to meet the thermal comfort needs of passengers. There are also some studies on designing and using TES-based air conditioning systems in EVs. Li et al. [69] investigated a TES system which

Fig. 3. Classification of TES technologies.

can be charged (cold energy storage mode) with electricity from grid when the EVs battery is charging, and discharged (cold energy release mode) to cool the cabin to the comfortable temperature while driving. The EVs can automatically be changed to use conventional air conditioning system for continuous cooling when the TES is fully discharged. Besides EVs, a research team from the University of Birmingham built a system as illustrated in Fig. 4 to study the performance of a TES based air conditioning system for trains. The testing results showed that the TES based air-conditioner can accomplish 15–20% energy savings and reduce cabin temperature fluctuations substantially.

Cabin heating also affects the travelling range of EVs to a large extent, especially in a cold and wet winter. To address this, vehicle coolant has been proposed to be a storage medium (sensible heat storage) for the provision of heating [70,71]. The vehicle coolant can be pre-heated by the grid electricity when EV is plugged in. During driving, the vehicle coolant can be used for cabin heating without consuming battery energy, leading to an increased driving mileage. There have been also studies on the use of very high temperature sensible heat-based TES (e.g., packed bed TES) for cabin heating. The conceptual design uses a stream of air heated up by a TES before mixed with other streams of ambient-temperature air to achieve a comfortable air temperature for cabin heating [72]. Clearly, good insulation is essential due to the high temperature condition of the TES. Currently, PCM-based TES solutions are being developed, which is regarded as one of the most promising technologies for commercial heating applications in EVs. Tohoku Electric Power designed an HVAC battery EV with a 180 kg TES cell containing 9.5 kWh latent heat and 9.5 kWh sensible heat in the cell for cabin heating under cold conditions [73]. The cell was shown to be able to maintain the cabin temperature at around 15 °C. Shahidinejad et al. [74] investigated the effect of utilizing PCM based TES for EV heating on the travelling range in cold weathers (0 °C to –20 °C). The PCM based TES is heated until the

melting point by an electrical heater connected to the power grid. Simulation results indicated that the PCM installed in seat cushions can help maintain the comfort temperature at 15 °C, leading to an increased travelling range by 21%. Wang et al. [75,76] designed and tested a PCM based TES system (termed as electrical PCM-Assisted Thermal Heating System - ePATHS) for cabin heating in EVs. The system was designed to provide enough thermal energy to heat the EV cabin for ~46 min, which can cover a daily round trip commute of a typical driver in America. The PCM is heated and melted using power from electrical grid while the EV is plugged in. This ePATHS can work in three modes for cabin heating: PCM discharging for heating, PCM and PTC (Positive Temperature Coefficient heater) joint heating, and PTC heating. Their results showed that the total travelling range can be improved by 26% compared with the EV with PTC heating only. Besides the academic research, practical industrial research has also been reported. For example, Sunamp Ltd applied for a patent of an automotive thermal battery energy storage which can be used for EV cabin heating and dehumidification [77].

If the working temperature and thermal properties of the TES materials can be properly selected and the control system is well designed, the TES can also show the potential to provide both cooling and heating for EVs. In 2011, Wu et al. [78] developed a HVAC system combined with water-storage heating and ice-storage cooling. It was found that the TES system could save almost 20% of the cost and increase the travelling range by 30%. Rezaei et al. [79] proposed the use of a PCM heat exchanger to replace the primary external heat exchanger in the reversed heat pump based HVAC system of EVs for both cooling and heating. The PCM is supposed to have a phase change temperature around the comfort temperature which is lower/higher than the ambient temperature in summer/winter, respectively. In this way, the energy consumption of the compressor can be reduced, and hence the travelling range of EVs can be increased. The PCM can be charged by running a heat pump

Fig. 4. Working principle of TES based air conditioning system on electrical trains.

cycle in reverse when the EV battery is charged by an external power source. Besides PCM, TCM-based TES can reach a higher energy storage density and achieve longer energy storage duration, which is expected to provide both heating and cooling for EVs [80–83]. Clearly, the system design would be more complicated, and the performance of the working medium needs to be further improved [84].

3.2. Battery thermal management

The battery pack performance has a significant impact on the travelling range and performance of EVs and hybrid EVs. It is very important to control the thermal behaviour of batteries, which requires an effective Battery Thermal Management System (BTMS) [85,86]. It has been reported that Li-ion battery should work within a temperature ranging from 20 to 55 °C, and exceeding this range may lead to serious problems with the batteries [87]. Simultaneously, the temperature difference among all cells must be less than 5 °C [88,89]. Currently, there have been several BTMSs developed, including forced air-, liquid-, thermoelectric cooler-, heat pipe- and PCM-based BTMSs [90,91].

Air-based BTMSs have been researched for decades and commercialized in some vehicles, e.g., Nissan Leaf, Audi Q5 and Mitsubishi i-MiEV [92]. However, air cooling exhibits significant drawbacks in terms of low cooling capacity and low efficiency which limit its application in high power density EVs [93]. To overcome the disadvantages of air cooling, liquid-based BTMSs have been investigated and commonly applied in some EVs such as Tesla Model S, Chevrolet Volt, Audi Q7, BMW i3 and i8 [94]. However, liquid cooling can cause increases in volume, system complexity, cost and parasitic power loss as well as leakage risk [95]. Passive BTMSs based on thermoelectric coolers, heat pipes and PCMs have also been suggested and studied. Among them, the utilization of PCM in BTMSs has attracted more attention and investigated very comprehensively due to advantages of more uniform temperature distribution, larger latent heat, simpler structure, lower power consumption and more affordable cost [96]. There have been several related review articles published in recent years [87,97,98]. The basic working principle of a PCM-based BTMS lies in the battery temperature controlled by the surrounding PCMs absorbing and releasing heat during phase change.

Paraffin is one of the most extensively studied organic PCMs for BTMS because of its stability, non-corrosiveness and appropriate phase change temperature range [99,100]. However, the PCM in pure form has limitations such as low thermal conductivity. Several methods have been developed to address this. Fig. 5 shows some common methods to enhance PCM-based BTMS performance [98]. These methods can be divided into hybrid BTMS (integrating PCM with other cooling strategies, e.g., liquid/air/heat pipe/thermoelectric-cooling, for BTMS), and modified PCM by encapsulation, the addition of thermally conductive particles, or metal meshes [87]. So far, the hybrid BTMS which integrates PCM with a heat pipe have been shown to have the best performance in terms of maximum temperature rise reduction and uniform temperature distribution across the cells without consuming external power [98].

3.3. Cold storage for refrigeration

Cold chain plays an important role in daily life because of the increased demand for fresh products and frozen foods, and medicine [101]. In addition to the use of TES for normal EVs to provide HVAC for passengers and the thermal management for batteries, TES can also contribute to cooling provision for trucks, trains, vessels, and aircrafts for cold chain transportation.

Fig. 5. Common methods to enhance PCM-based BTMSs working performance [98].

Many efforts have been done to integrate TES with traditional refrigeration units for energy performance enhancement and carbon emission reduction [102,103]. For instance, PCM-based insulation for refrigerated vans [104] and refrigerated shipping containers [105] have been proposed for decreasing heat load and energy consumption. In recent years, TES-based cold chain without any external energy supply during transportation have been actively pursued [106]. For example, University of Birmingham has been working with one of China's largest railway rolling stock companies, CRRC Shijiazhuang, to develop the technology, leading to the world's first road/rail container with PCMs for cold energy storage. The PCM inside the container is charged first (storing cold as shown in Fig. 6) for use to keep the inside temperature between 4 and 12 °C for up to 120 h (releasing cold) without a power supply nor a refrigeration unit [107,108]. This first-of-a-kind refrigerated PCM-based shipping container technology can be transferred from train to truck and vice versa, which is easier and more efficient to operate than conventional refrigeration equipment. This technology has completed commercial trial carrying real goods for several tens of thousands of kilometres on road and rail across different climate zones. In addition, this PCM-based container can be used for cold chain transportation of different goods with different temperature requirements through the use of different PCMs (Table 1) [109,110]. Another promising application area for TES in refrigeration is for transporting Antarctic Ice Cores [111]. Scientists from the University of Birmingham has been working on Ice Core portable box design including PCM screening, formulation, and manufacturing, insulation panel selection, overall internal arrangement of ice cores in the box, by modelling and experiments. This Ice Core carrying box has been demonstrated under simulated conditions to be able to transporting the drilled ice cores from Villum station in Greenland to BAS in Cambridge over 20 h, as illustrated in Fig. 7.

4. Challenges and opportunities

Thermal energy provision in EVs currently originates from the central power source, i.e., Li-ion battery packs, by consuming

Fig. 6. Charging process of the PCM-based shipping container for cold chain transportation.

Table 1
Temperature requirements for cold chain transportation.

Good	Temperature requirement	Examples
Deep frozen food	-36 °C	Tuna
Frozen food	-12/-18/-25 °C	Frozen meat/seafood, ice cream
Chilled food	-2/-5 °C	Chilled meat/seafood
Refrigeration	-2 to 7 °C	Dairy, fruits, vegetables
Preservation	7 to 15 °C	Fruits, vegetables
Constant temperature	15 to 25 °C	Wine, chocolate, coffee beans
Covid-19 vaccine storage	2 to 8 °C	AstraZeneca
	-25 to -15 °C	Moderna
	-90 to -60 °C	Pfizer

Fig. 7. Transportation route for Antarctic Ice Cores.

electricity. Both the energy recovery and storage technologies for EVs have been aimed to save more electrical energy for driving thereby stretching the travelling range, alleviating range anxiety, and improving energy efficiency. The advantages of applying TES technologies in EVs lie in two aspects:

- Thermal energy storage technologies enable the desired heat or coldness to originate from centralised thermal generating facilities (with a higher system level efficiency due to shorter conversion and transmission chain) instead of a standalone on-board air conditioning system (with a lower system level efficiency). The running cost of such TES is likely to be much lower than consuming electricity stored in the battery.
- Zero-emission thermal energy management due to solar energy for heating in winter and seasonal cooling in summer, energy from geographical temperature differences, and geothermal energy can be stored for different spatial or temporal needs, i.e., heating or cooling of the cabin or battery thermal management. This can reduce the use of high grade electrical energy for lower grade heating applications, and optimises energy consumption of EVs for range extension.

There are a number of challenges for these mobile energy recovery and storage technologies. Among main ones are -

- Limited energy efficiency associated with energy recovery, conversion, storage and utilization technologies;

- The lack of existing infrastructure and services for multi-vector energy EV charging.

Associated with the second challenge above, there is a need for access to rapidly updated information via GPS or mobile apps to locate the nearest refuelling stations for both electrical and thermal recharge.

5. Conclusions and visions

The race to net-zero has led to a rapid increase in the number of EVs on the road around the world. The evolution of EVs depends on the development of energy storage technologies to increase travelling range and associated charging infrastructure, which are of great concern to consumers. This paper provides a brief state-of-the-art review on both energy recovery and thermal energy storage technologies with a potential for use in EVs to help address the challenges. The characteristics and possible adaptive development of such energy recovery and storage technologies are briefly discussed in terms of energy conversion efficiencies, energy density, applicable scenarios, technical development status, and cost. We have also identified the following medium- and long-term research needs:

Energy conversion technologies for EVs: Energy conversion efficiency enhancement is needed for future deployment of thermoelectric, piezoelectric, and triboelectric devices in EVs. Specifically, nanotriboelectrification based on liquid intrusion/extrusion

Fig. 8. A vision for future multi-energy-vector charging infrastructure for EVs.

in non-wetting porous media could impact automobile industry, particularly in terms of EV range extension and efficiency enhancement.

TES technologies for EVs: TES technologies provides a solution for efficient EV thermal management and range extension. There is a need for the development of thermal energy charging devices and infrastructure in parallel to the electrical charging infrastructure. For doing so, TES materials requires further development to improve their energy density and charging/discharging kinetics.

Infrastructure for multi-energy-vector powered EVs: Multi-energy powered EVs require the establishment of multi-vector energy charging stations and associated infrastructure, as well as the access to rapidly updated charge station locations through e.g. GPS and mobile phone apps. This could consist of a network of distributed thermal energy harvest, storage and charging hubs co-located with electrical charging stations for the provision of electrical and thermal energy to EVs. Fig. 8 shows such a vision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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